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ECTOPIC ACROMEGALY DUE TO NEUROENDOCRINE LUNG TUMORS: FIRST DESCRIPTION OF THREE CLINICAL CASES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. *Acromegaly is a neuroendocrine disease that occurs as a result of excess production of growth hormone (somatotrophic hormone, GH). In most cases, the cause of acromegaly is pituitary adenomas that produce GH. Cases of ectopic acromegaly are much less common. The latter occurs due to tumors that produce growth hormone-releasing hormone (GRHR), or tumors of extrapituitary localization that produce GH. The main sources of GHRH secretion are neuroendocrine tumors (NETs) of the lungs and pancreas. Treatment of ectopic acromegaly consists of surgical removal of the source of overproduction of GHRH, and if radical removal is not possible, long-acting somatostatin analogues, pegvisomant, chemotherapy, immunotherapy, and radiation therapy are used. This article describes three clinical cases of ectopic acromegaly due to GHRH-producing pulmonary NETs, each of which is notable for a number of features. In the first two cases, acromegaly had a mild course and mild clinical manifestations, while in case 2 there was a combination of ectopic acromegaly and primary hyperparathyroidism. In case 3, ectopic acromegaly was combined with a pituitary macroadenoma, and after surgical treatment of NET, remission of acromegaly did not occur. In all three cases, pulmonary NETs were discovered incidentally during chest X-ray examination for other conditions.*

Key words: *ectopic acromegaly; neuroendocrine tumors; growth hormone-releasing hormone; primary hyperparathyroidism; pituitary macroadenoma.*

ЭКТОПИЧЕСКАЯ АКРОМЕГАЛИЯ НА ФОНЕ НЕЙРОЭНДОКРИННЫХ ОПУХОЛЕЙ ЛЕГКИХ: ПЕРВОЕ ОПИСАНИЕ ТРЕХ КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ СЛУЧАЕВ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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Аннотация. Акромегалия – нейроэндокринное заболевание, вызванное избыточной выработкой гормона роста (ГР). Чаще всего причиной акромегалии являются аденомы гипофиза, продуцирующие ГР. Эктопическая акромегалия встречается реже и может быть вызвана опухолями, выделяющими ГР или ГРГР. Источниками избыточной секреции GHRH могут быть нейроэндокринные опухоли легких и поджелудочной железы. Лечение ectopic акромегалии включает хирургическое удаление источника GHRH, а также применение аналогов соматостатина, пегвисоманта, химиотерапии, иммунотерапии и лучевой терапии. В статье описаны три клинических случая ectopic акромегалии, вызванной легочными опухолями, каждый с уникальными особенностями. В некоторых случаях акромегалия имела легкое течение и небольшие клинические проявления. Также описано сочетание ectopic акромегалии и первичного гиперпаратиреоза. В одном наблюдении ectopic акромегалия сочеталась с макроаденомой гипофиза, и после хирургического лечения не наступила ремиссия акромегалии. Легочные опухоли были обнаружены случайно при рентгенологическом исследовании грудной клетки для других состояний..

Ключевые слова: ectopic акромегалия; нейроэндокринные опухоли; гормон роста, высвобождающий гормон; первичный гиперпаратиреоз; макроаденома гипофиза.

Introduction. Acromegaly is a severe chronic neuroendocrine disease that occurs as a result of excess production of growth hormone (somatotrophic hormone, GH) [1]. In more than 95% of cases, the cause of acromegaly is pituitary adenomas that produce GH (both sporadic and familial forms) [2, 3]. Much less common (less than 5%) are cases of ectopic acromegaly [4]. The term “ectopic acromegaly” essentially combines three concepts. Firstly, these are tumors that produce growth hormone-releasing hormone (somatoliberin, GHRH), which, in turn, stimulates excess production of growth hormone by the intact pituitary gland. These include both hypothalamic tumors (hamartomas, gliomas, gangliocytomas), in which hyperplasia and then a GH-producing pituitary adenoma can develop, as well as neuroendocrine tumors (NETs) or, rarely, tumors of a non-neuroendocrine nature of various localizations that produce GHRH [5]. Secondly, ectopic pituitary adenomas producing growth hormone, located outside the sella turcica - in the sphenoid sinus, pyramid of the temporal bone, nasopharyngeal cavity [6]. Thirdly, extracranial tumors that produce GH (for example, pancreatic NET [7], non-Hodgkin's lymphoma [8]). The first description of ectopic acromegaly dates back to 1949, when Goldman described a patient with a combination of a lung NET, a pituitary tumor, and bilateral adrenal masses, suggesting that the lung tumor produced a factor that stimulated the growth of tumors in other organs [cited in 5]. The role of a lung tumor as a cause of acromegaly was first demonstrated by Altmann and Schütz, who in 1959 reported a patient with clinical manifestations of acromegaly who did not experience remission of the disease after pituitary irradiation, but markedly improved after resection of a lung tumor [cited in 9]. In 1982, two independent groups isolated a protein that stimulates the production of GH (termed GHRH) from pancreatic tumor tissue from two patients with acromegaly [10, 11], which allowed us to establish a causal relationship between the development of acromegaly and the presence of a tumor located in an extrapituitary location. By 2012, Garby et al. published a literature review summarizing data on 53 known cases of ectopic acromegaly [12], and Ghazy et al. — data on 98 cases [13]. In 2022, Zendran et al. published a review summarizing data on 127 known cases [14]. In general, in 2/3 of cases, ectopic acromegaly is detected in women [13], and the main sources of GHRH secretion in ectopic acromegaly are NETs of the lungs (typical and atypical lung carcinoids) (up to 43%) and pancreas (up to 35%) [14]. In isolated cases, pheochromocytomas, paragangliomas, lymphomas, thymomas and some other tumors may occur [12–14]. In only two cases, GHRH-producing tumors were not of a neuroendocrine nature (diffuse large B-cell lymphoma [15] and

adenoid cystic lung carcinoma [16]). Among intracranial sources of ectopic GHRH production, mixed gangliocytomas-pituitary adenomas are more common [14]. The clinical picture of ectopic acromegaly does not differ from that of typical acromegaly, and it can be suspected in the absence of visualization of the pituitary adenoma according to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain or in the detection of diffuse pituitary hyperplasia [17]. The difficulty in diagnosing ectopic acromegaly lies in finding the source of GHRH production, and the main treatment method is removal of the primary tumor [13, 14]. If radical tumor removal is not possible, long-acting somatostatin analogues, pegvisomant, chemotherapy, immunotherapy, and radiation therapy may be prescribed [13, 14]. The article describes three clinical cases of ectopic acromegaly due to GHRH-producing NETs of the lungs, each of which is notable for a number of features. In Russia, clinical cases of ectopic acromegaly have not been previously described.

DESCRIPTIONS OF CASES

Case 1 Patient S.N.Yu. Born in 1962, she was first hospitalized at the State Scientific Center of the Russian Federation, Federal State Budgetary Institution “National Medical Research Center of Endocrinology” of the Ministry of Health of Russia at the age of 58 years. She considered herself sick for 6–7 years, when she began to notice changes in appearance (swelling of the face, increase in the size of the feet), weight loss, general weakness, and irritability. During a routine examination by a gynecologist in 2014, acromegaly was suspected and an MRI of the brain was recommended, during which a pituitary microadenoma was visualized. A hormonal blood test revealed hyperprolactinemia (initial data not provided); cabergoline therapy was prescribed at a dose of 0.25 mg once a week, against the background of which normalization of prolactin levels was achieved. In 2015, elevated concentrations of insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) and growth hormone were determined for the first time, and a diagnosis of “Acromegaly” was established. During a follow-up MRI examination in 2016, a pituitary microadenoma measuring 5x5 mm remained. Since September 2016, due to persistent normoprolactinemia, cabergoline was discontinued, and drug therapy for acromegaly was started with somatostatin analogs—long-acting octreotide 20 mg intramuscularly once every 28 days, which she received for 6 months. During treatment, the patient noted an improvement in her health, but IGF-1 remained elevated. Due to poor tolerability of octreotide (induration and hyperemia at injection sites), therapy was discontinued. In December 2016, hyperprolactinemia up to 1098 mU/l was again detected, cabergoline therapy was periodically resumed and discontinued. No changes in the size of the pituitary adenoma were observed during drug treatment

with somatostatin analogues and cabergoline. 68 | Problems of Endocrinology
CLINICAL CASE In February 2017, during a routine fluorography, a mass formation in the patient's left lung was detected for the first time. Multislice computed tomography (MSCT) described a formation in the root of the left lung with clear, even contours, dimensions 44x42x50 mm, heterogeneous density with small calcium inclusions, density 32–30 units N. The formation was suspicious for malignant growth, so in May 2017, a typical segmentectomy of S4-5 on the left and lymphadenectomy was performed at the oncology clinic at the place of residence. According to the immunohistochemical (IHC) study of the removed tumor, a well-differentiated lung NET, Grade 1, with a Ki-67 proliferation index of less than 2% was verified, which is typical for a typical carcinoid. In the postoperative period, the patient noted a significant improvement in her health: return to her original weight (body weight gain of 18 kg), disappearance of facial swelling, and reduction in general weakness. With dynamic monitoring of hormonal parameters, normalization of the levels of IGF-1 and growth hormone was achieved. After MSCT, no evidence of tumor recurrence was obtained. Due to complaints of back pain, an x-ray of the spine was performed, a compression fracture was detected 12th thoracic vertebra, a diagnosis was made: "Osteoporosis of mixed origin" and antiresorptive therapy was prescribed. While cabergoline was discontinued and acromegaly was achieved in remission, attention was paid to the continued increase in monomeric prolactin to 1116 mU/l (64–395). To exclude possible secondary causes of the increase level of prolactin, the patient was examined for gynecological diseases - no pathology was found. Of the possible causes of hyperprolactinemia, the patient has fibrocystic mastopathy. Considering the moderate increase in prolactin levels, the achievement of normoprolactinemia while taking a small dose of cabergoline, the lack of positive dynamics in the growth of the pituitary adenoma, pituitary microadenoma is considered as hormonally inactive. Considering the combination of pituitary microadenoma and lung NET, a screening examination was carried out for possible components of MEN-1 syndrome: no data were obtained for primary hyperparathyroidism (PHPT), space-occupying lesions of the pancreas or adrenal glands. Blood test for chromogranin A - 2.1 nmol/l (less than 2).

Conclusion. Acromegaly is relatively rare in the general population, and ectopic acromegaly in its structure occurs only in about 5% of cases. However, endocrinologists should suspect the presence of ectopic acromegaly in the absence of visualization of a pituitary adenoma or in the detection of diffuse pituitary hyperplasia, hypointense on T2-weighted images, according to brain MRI. The

diagnostic search should begin with the exclusion of NETs of the lungs and pancreas, and if a NET of the pancreas is detected, MEN-1 syndrome should be suspected. Surgical treatment is the treatment of choice because it has the potential to completely remove the source of GHRH overproduction and lead to remission of acromegaly. In the absence of remission of ectopic acromegaly after surgical treatment, it is advisable to prescribe various drug treatment options.

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